

“OPEN ACCESS TRAINING MATERIAL FOR TEACHERS AND RESEARCHERS”

D5.3: “OA training material for teachers and researchers”

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CITIZEN SCIENCE: AN INTRODUCTORY GUIDE FOR RESEARCHERS

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
STEAM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
SwafS	Science with and for Society
A/N	Author’s note

1. Introduction

Citizen Science has emerged as a transformative approach to research, redefining the boundaries between scientists and the public. By involving non-professional scientists in data collection, analysis, and even hypothesis formulation, this methodology democratizes science, making it more accessible, inclusive, and impactful. This deliverable aims to promote Citizen Science among researchers by providing a comprehensive overview of its principles, applications, and benefits, particularly within the European context.

Structured to guide researchers through the fundamentals of Citizen Science, the deliverable starts with an introduction to the concept and its alignment with frameworks like Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and Open Science. It then explores the rationale behind Europe's strong commitment to Citizen Science, highlighting its successes and the European Commission's strategic support.

Moving beyond theoretical discussions, this deliverable delves into the tangible impact of Citizen Science on research methodologies and societal outcomes. From understanding its role in fostering trust in science to its ethical implications and contributions to outreach, the document showcases how Citizen Science transcends traditional engagement models.

Lastly, through selected project examples and reflective insights, the deliverable illustrates the transformative potential of Citizen Science for both researchers and society. By bridging scientific rigor with citizen engagement, this approach not only enriches the scientific process but also fosters a culture of collaborative innovation essential for addressing the complex challenges of our time.

2. What is Citizen Science?

How to help people to properly inform themselves, understand and face collective choices in full awareness? Are science, involvement, and bottom-up participation reconcilable ideas?

The recent pandemic highlighted the scepticism in public opinion towards science: now more than ever we need correct and reliable scientific communication, and we need to find a common ground between the scientists and the public to increase their awareness of the scientific method and their involvement in collective choices.

Moreover, several global crises are now posing a challenge to all societies around the world, but “*there are scientific recommendations, but no social consensus for implementation*”¹: the loss of biodiversity, climate change, and emerging zoonotic diseases need **the commitment and efforts of everyone**, policymakers, industry, science, and civil society included, to ensure healthy and resilient societies.

The connection between science and society is therefore an increasingly crucial factor for a democratic development that allows citizens to make the proper choices for their lives and for the society itself. *Citizen Science* or “**science made by citizens**” can help citizens to understand and share not only the meaning and the value of scientific research, but also its effects in everyday life and for a good standard of living, especially when applied to the local context in which citizens live. Citizen Science is therefore **a tool** that can connect different spheres of

1. European Commission (2022), The transformative potential of Citizen Science, Magazine of European Research Council, <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/transformative-potential-citizen-science>

society and a **bona fide scientific methodology** that, when done correctly, has the potential to influence important policy decisions.

The **definition of Citizen Science** given by the European Commission is ²:

/ˈsɪt.ɪ.zən ˌsaɪ.əns/

“ *Citizen Science is the voluntary participation of non-professional scientists in research and innovation, at different stages of the process and at different levels of engagement: from defining research programs and policies to collecting, processing and analyzing data and evaluating research results.* ”

Citizen Science isn't just a buzzword...

- It's a movement, a collaboration between passionate individuals, coming together to contribute our knowledge, skills, and curiosity to scientific endeavours.
- It's about harnessing the power of collective intelligence to solve real-world problems.
- Citizen Science has the potential to revolutionize how we approach scientific discovery, making it more inclusive, diverse, and impactful.

2. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation - European Commission Citizen Science, 2020, Elevating research and innovation through societal engagement, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d1768147-f17a-11ea-991b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-152465380>

2.1 Ten principles of Citizen Science

In 2015 the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) promoted the drafting of the *10 principles of Citizen Science*³, with the aim of finding common aspects and guidelines valid for all initiatives and these ten principles have been translated into the 27 languages of the European Union, to give them the greatest possible dissemination.

Here the 10 principles:

1. Citizen Science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates **new knowledge or understanding**. Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.
2. Citizen Science projects have a **genuine science outcome**. For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.
3. **Both the professional scientists and the Citizen Scientists benefit from taking part**. Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy.
4. Citizen Scientists may, if they wish, participate **in multiple stages** of the scientific process. This may include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.
5. Citizen Scientists **receive feedback** from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.
6. Citizen Science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for. However, unlike traditional research approaches, Citizen Science provides **opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation of science**.
7. Citizen Science **project data and meta-data are made publicly available** and where possible, results are published in an open access format. Data sharing may occur during or after the project, unless there are security or privacy concerns that prevent this.
8. Citizen Scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.
9. Citizen Science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, **data quality**, participant experience and wider societal or **policy impact**.
10. The leaders of Citizen Science projects **take into consideration legal and ethical issues** surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities.

3. European Citizen Science Association, 2015, *Ten Principles of Citizen Science*, <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>

2.2 Pillars of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) engages public and accountable stakeholders to achieve research and innovation results that are:

- Ethically acceptable
- Sustainable
- Socially desirable

The rationale behind RRI is that science and technology have the potential to change the future, but this can happen if citizens, industry, and other societal stakeholders are involved in the process.

A key mechanism within RRI is the **quadruple helix model**, which broadens the traditional triad of involved stakeholders by incorporating civil society as a fourth essential partner:

1. Academia
2. Policy makers
3. Industry & SMEs
4. Citizens

This model encourages co-creation, where citizens actively participate not just as data contributors but as equal collaborators in shaping research agendas and evaluating outcomes. By leveraging the unique insights and expertise of each group, the quadruple helix model bridges the gap between science and society, fostering innovations that are sustainable, inclusive, and socially robust. All stakeholders are involved in a dynamic and iterative process, interacting and sharing responsibilities regarding the results of RRI processes.

RRI is based on 6 pillars that are: Public Engagement, Open Science, Research Integrity and Ethics, Science education, Gender equality, and Governance (Figure 1) ⁴. Accordingly, core principles for responsibly conducting research and innovation are anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, responsiveness, openness, and transparency.

Figure 1 – Six pillars of RRI.

4. D.-G. for R. and I. European Commission, Responsible research and innovation: Europe's ability to respond to societal challenges, (2014). <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2be36f74-b490-409e-bb60-12fd438100fe/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>

Citizen Science is positioned at the interface between Public Engagement and Open Science (Figure 1), but it can also incorporate all 6 dimensions of RRI ⁵:

Public Engagement, engaging citizens and other stakeholders to collaborate within the research and innovation ecosystem and address social challenges;

Open Science, making science accessible and unrestricted;

Integrity and ethics of research, linking research to the 10 principles of Citizen Science and considering related ethical issues;

Gender equality, promoting gender balance and the inclusion of gender and sex issues in research and Innovation, and all participatory activities, including communication used to engage women;

Science education, encouraging scientific literacy and critical thinking, and promoting STEAM (Science Technology Engineering Art and Maths) careers;

Governance, fostering liaisons with legislators to encourage official use of citizen-generated data and evidence-based policies.

5. Adapted from Rosa Arias, *The Citizen Science Funding Landscape*, TIME4CS webinar 9.3.23

2.3. Open Science and cross-cutting issues

The European Commission adopted an **Open Science Policy**⁶, an approach to the scientific process focused on spreading knowledge as soon as it is available, by using digital and collaborative technology.

Open science builds on several key pillars, with open access, scientific publications, infrastructures, educational resources, data, resources, software, and hardware, crowdfunding and crowdsourcing, open engagement of societal actors, and open dialogue with other knowledge systems. Citizen Science is one of these pillars^{7,8}.

The novel impact-driven approach of research programmes also highlights the importance of **cross-cutting issues** for the development of research activities. They are a **mandatory requirement** to be competitive (and eligible) at European and national levels⁹. The cross-cutting issues are listed here:

- Gender equality and inclusiveness
- Ethics and Integrity
- Dissemination Exploitation
- Socio-economic sciences
- Open science practices
- Key Enabling Technologies
- Social Innovation
- EU taxonomy

Citizen Science can help to focus on community-driven needs, and it may be a tool to tackle many of these cross-cutting issues. It is now considered part of the excellence criterion during proposal evaluation and one of the indicators to measure Horizon Europe impact.

6. European Commission, *Open Science* https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en#the-eus-open-science-policy

7. UNESCO, UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>.

8. UNESCO, Towards a UNESCO Recommendation on Open science (2020), https://en.unesco.org/sites/default/files/open_science_brochure_en.pdf.

9. Horizon Europe HE Programme Guide V4.1 (2024) https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

3. Why Citizen Science in Europe?

3.1 A story of success

Citizen Science is gaining more and more ground in Europe, with projects paying special attention to environmental issues. A recent study¹⁰ provides interesting data on this growing trend. The study analysed 157 Citizen Science projects in Europe participating in the Horizon 2020 program, mainly from Spain (37%), Portugal (17%) and Italy (11%). The results show that most projects focus on environmental and land issues (66.5%), with a particular focus on biodiversity (35.6%).

SwafS (Science with and for Society) was one of the components of Horizon 2020, the former European Union research and innovation program, focused on emphasizing the social dimension of science, by integrating the participation of citizens and other societal stakeholders in research, decision-making, and innovation processes. It was a strategic orientation towards public participation, that included:

- building the territorial dimension of SwafS
- exploring support for Citizen Science
- strengthening knowledge through SwafS

SwafS helped identify four main **objectives of Citizen Science**, to be embedded transversally in all Horizon Missions and Clusters:

- Building effective cooperation between science and society;
- Recruiting new talent for science;
- Pairing scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility;
- Ensuring a more responsible science and enabling the development of policies more relevant to society at large.

SwafS aided in broadening the scope of scientific research, making science more accessible, transparent, and socially responsible: the objectives and principles of SwafS have been then integrated across Horizon Europe rather than being treated as a dedicated area. These themes are now embedded in various parts of the program, particularly in **Pillar II** ("Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness") and in the **Missions of Horizon Europe**, which aim to increase societal involvement in the co-design and co-creation of solutions¹¹.

Here we listed examples of activities fostered in Horizon Europe:

- **Co-designed activities:** workshops, focus groups or other means to develop R&I agendas, roadmaps and policies, often including deep discussion on the implications, the ethics, the benefits and the challenges related to R&I courses of actions and technology development;
- **Co-creation activities:** involving citizens or end-users directly in the development of new knowledge or innovation, for instance through Citizen Science and user-led innovation;
- **Co-assessment activities:** such as assisting in the monitoring, evaluation and feedback to the governance of a project, policies or programmes on an iterative or even continual basis.

10. Giardullo, P., Neresini, F., Marín-González, E., Luís, C., Magalhães, J. and Arias, R. (2023). *Citizen Science and participatory science communication: an empirically informed discussion connecting research and theory*, Journal of Science Communication, <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.22020201>

11. European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021), Horizon Europe Strategic Plan (2021 – 2024), <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/083753>

3.2 Why the European Commission is supporting Citizen Science?

European Commission contributes to foster and finance Citizens Science projects¹² because they are characterized by:

3.2.1 Excellence:

- They broaden the scope of R&I and the quality and quantity of data collected, discussed and analysed
- They increase the robustness of results
- They enable innovative and creative approaches
- They harness collective intelligence (often excluded from contributing to Research & Innovation)

3.2.2 Effectiveness:

- They align results with society's needs, values and expectations, ensuring greater relevance and adoption
- They reduce time-to-market for innovative products and services
- They trigger behavioural changes

3.2.3 Rise in society's trust in science:

- They increase openness, transparency and 'co-ownership' of society
- They often lead to more inclusive outcomes
- They encourage mutual learning between science and society

12. Farrer, L., Delaney N., 27-10-2021, *Citizen and societal engagement: A policy and programme priority for the European Commission*, EU-Citizen Science event, <https://eu-citizen.science/static/site/files/Citizen%20and%20societal%20engagement%20-%20Niamh%20Delaney%20and%20Linden%20Farrer.pdf>

3.3 Did you know that...¹³

...the platform eu-citizen.science was officially launched on March 3, 2020, as part of a project funded under Horizon 2020?

The project began in January 2019 and concluded in December 2021

The platform was developed through a consortium of 14 partners and 9 third parties from 13 European countries and the United Kingdom, including universities, NGOs, local authorities, and research institutions. Notable contributors included Museum für Naturkunde (Berlin), European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), University College London (UCL), Ecsite.

...the platform is crucial for promoting cross-border cooperation and advancing scientific discovery through public participation?

The platform is a tool for cross-border cooperation and scientific discovery because it provides a collaborative space for projects, resources, and networking. By using this platform, researchers can increase the visibility of their Citizen Science projects, recruit new participants, and enhance the impact of their work on a broader scale. Besides, it also serves as a hub for learning, providing valuable tools and best practices for designing and managing Citizen Science initiatives.

13. *Periodic Reporting for period 2 - EU-Citizen.Science (The Platform for Sharing, Initiating, and Learning Citizen Science in Europe)*, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824580/reporting>

4. Citizen Science impact

4.1 Impact: beneficiaries

There are two different categories of impact based on beneficiaries¹⁴ to be considered in the novel European impact-driven approach of research programmes:

- **Academic impact** is the demonstrable contribution that excellent research makes to academic advances, across and within disciplines, including significant advances in understanding, method, theory and application.
- **Societal and Economic impact** is the demonstrable contribution that excellent research makes to society and the economy, of benefit to individuals, organizations and nations. In the societal and economic impact, we can point out other subcategories that differ from each other based on the scope of the project. Projects may have a:
 - **Cultural impact** because they contribute to people’s understanding of ideas, values, and beliefs;
 - **Economic impact** because they contribute to a company’s costs and revenues and economic returns through increased productivity or economic growth;
 - **Educational impact** because they contribute to capacity-building and training, through curricula, educational tools and qualifications;
 - **Environmental impact** because they contribute to managing the environment (reducing pollution, tackling climate crisis);
 - **Health impact** because they contribute to life expectancy, health-related quality of life, and prevention of illness;
 - **Political impact** because they contribute to how policies are constructed;
 - **Social impact** because they contribute to community welfare and quality of life;
 - **Technological impact** because they contribute to the creation or improvement of products and services.

4.2 Impact: time

Impact can also vary over time, with the aim of strengthening the uptake of R&I in society with different levels at different stages.

- **Short-term impact** regards the co-creation and it can be measured by the number and share of projects funded by the Programme where citizens and end-users contribute to the co-creation of R&I content;
- **Medium-term impact** regards engagement and it can be measured by the number and share of participating legal entities which have citizen and end-user engagement mechanisms in place after the end of projects;
- **Longer-term impact** regards societal R&I uptake and it results in the uptake and outreach of co-created scientific results and innovative solutions generated under the project lifespan.

14. What is Research Impact? <https://stories.nuigalway.ie/what-is-research-impact-/index.html>

5. Citizen Science as a research methodology

Citizen Science is a *de facto* research methodology. Just like any other, it has advantages and disadvantages: in a research laboratory, all conditions are controlled, which allows causal conclusions to be drawn. In the real world, we can reach communities that would probably never come to a laboratory. The strength lies in the combination of methods, where the disadvantages of one method can be offset by the advantages of another¹⁵.

Let's see how this is possible.

5.1 How many Citizen Science projects?

The forms of Citizen Science that we see today are very different from the past. In fact, it is now an activity that can be **carried out by everyone**, whereas once it was only for few interested individuals¹⁶. From the initial collaborative role in data collection, citizens have now also participated in the formulation of research questions, the creation of methods and the analysis of the data themselves¹⁷. The ways in which citizens participate in projects can be many: some make their own local resources available (such as, for example, their backyard), others share the computational resources of their PCs, and still others provide their cognitive skills in data analysis.

Citizen Science has spread in recent years mainly due to advances in technology, particularly the Internet and mobile devices as these tools have made it easy for people to contribute using specific Apps and share their observations¹⁸ generating data that would otherwise be difficult or expensive to obtain¹⁹.

Citizen Science projects can therefore be classified according to **volunteer engagement**²⁰ (figure 2), usually paralleled by a decrease in the leadership and control played on the project by the “professional” researchers.

15. Crone, E. (2022) *Knowledge is everywhere*, European Research Council Magazine, <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/knowledge-everywhere>

16. Silvertown, J. (2009) *A new dawn for Citizen Science*. Trends in Ecology, Evolution 24(9): 467-471, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.03.017>

17. Cooper, C.B., Lewenstein, B.V. (2016) *Two meanings of Citizen Science*. in Cavalier, D., Kennedy E.B. (Eds.) The Rightful Place of Science: Citizen Science, pp. 51-62, AZ: Consortium for Science, Policy, Outcomes, Tempe

18. Newman, G., Wiggins, A., Crall, A., Graham, G., Newman, S., Crowston, K. (2012) *The future of Citizen Science: Emerging technologies and shifting paradigms*, Front Ecol Environment 6(10): 298-304. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110294>

19. Cohn, J.P. (2008) *Citizen Science: Can Volunteers Do Real Research?*, BioScience 58(3): 192-197. <https://doi.org/10.1641/B580303>

20. Haklay, M. (2013) *Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation*, Crowdsourcing Geogr. Knowl., Springer Netherlands, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7

Figure 2 – Classification of Citizen Science projects according to volunteer engagement and four illustrative projects^{21,22,23,24}

21. <https://www.mountainnow.net/en/>

22. <https://www.thekidstrial.ie/>

23. <https://www.citieshealth.eu/>

24. Peplow, M. (2018) *The Flint water crisis: how citizen scientists exposed poisonous politics*, 559: 180

<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-05651-7>

According to the type of project, not only can the percentage of volunteer engagement vary, but also which kind of data is collected²⁵ (figure 3).

Figure 3 – Collection of data in Citizen Science projects

Obviously, the more people participate, the more accurate the data will be, corroborating the chances of an accurate answer to the scientific problem investigated and reducing the probability of biased observations. Moreover, a vast amount of data can be collected in a shorter time.

5.2 The scientific process

Citizen Science is a scientific approach like any other. The design of any scientific project - in science and Citizen Science – is at its best when it is specific, that is when the question to be addressed is clear²⁵. Then, it involves the selection of a sampling scale and a level of precision for data collection that matches the question, as well as selecting a minimum sample size that addresses the variability inherent in the system. Once the data are collected, the post-processing step involves refining an analytic approach suited to the data and the question. The final step in science is presenting the work in a peer-reviewed publication²⁶.

25. Pocock, M.J.O., Chapman, D.S., Sheppard, L.J. & Roy, H.E. (2014). *Choosing and Using Citizen Science: a guide to when and how to use Citizen Science to monitor biodiversity and the environment*. Centre for Ecology & Hydrology

https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/sepa_choosingandusingcitizenscience_interactive_4web_final_amended-blue1.pdf

26. Parrish, J.K., Burgess, H., Weltzin, J.F., Fortson, L., Wiggins, A., and Simmons, B. (2018), *Exposing the Science in Citizen Science: Fitness to Purpose and Intentional Design*, Integrative and Comparative Biology, <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icy032>

All scientific projects have the following six main phases²⁶: Besides these common elements, Citizen Science presents other peculiar aspects that are fundamental to assure citizen participation, the creation of shared knowledge and a collection of data comparable in quality to that performed by professionals. Below, these elements are listed under each main phase.

1) Design

- matching tasks to the participant ability
- making goals explicit to participants

2) Development

- training:
- expert-designed
- in person
- online
- materials creation:
- participant-tested protocol
- cost scalable
- simple and tough
- sampling error design:
- multiple data collectors
- evidence
- over-sampling

3) Delivery

- number of ceiling:
- participants limits
- number of participants
- participant testing:
- pre- and post-training
- in program (accuracy)

4) Data ingestion

- transcription error evaluation:
- contemporaneous collection/entry
- post-event entry

5) Post-processing

- quality control procedures

6) Publication/use

- real-world decision making
- data stratification and visualization

5.3 Characteristics of a well-designed Citizen Science project

For citizen science data to be fit-for-purpose, the purpose needs to be clearly defined together with the level of engagement, the availability of resources, the scale of sampling, the complexity of the protocol, and the motivation of participants²⁵.

A project in which:

- the driving question is clear
- the engagement is an important part of the process
- there are plenty of resources available
- a large-scale sampling is needed
- a simple protocol is proposed to participants
- good reasons to participate are given

can apply the Citizen Science approach at its best.

Citizen science, however, is not a “*one-size-fits-all*” approach. Not all research projects, in fact, are suited to the collaborative, decentralized approach that characterizes Citizen Science. There might be projects with narrowly defined objectives, a high level of expertise, specialized equipment, or advanced techniques that may be better served by traditional research methods.

Citizen Science should be exploited only when it is able to give an **added value** to the project.

5.4 The researcher’s perspective

In parallel with the process of democratisation of science, Citizen Science plays a revolutionary role in disrupting the *ivory tower paradigm*, that posits that true knowledge can be achieved only in research institutes or universities. This paradigm is reductive and not inclusive, failing to recognize that many usable notions are available outside the academia.

The process of accepting the value of Citizen Science is still in progress, but scientists are finally recognizing its importance and benefits. The *conditio sine qua non* for a Citizen Science project is therefore that researchers exercise a certain degree of “humility” to step back and learn from others, resulting in a mutually beneficial relationship between science and society.

Scientists are generally on the one hand willing to participate in outreach activities like public talks or interviews, on the other less open to engaging lay people in their own research activities. Researchers may have negative perceptions of the public’s ability to contribute to science, because of the lack of specific knowledge, skills, and training of volunteer participants. According to the *deficit model*, in fact, the main reason for citizen scepticism towards modern science is their lack of sufficient science knowledge. However, involving citizens in the scientific process of gaining knowledge will result in a mutually beneficial relationship between science and society.

5.5 Quality control

A perceived stigma around Citizen Science projects in the scientific community (also explainable by a higher standard being placed on those types of projects when compared to a more traditional research method) results in scepticism towards data collected by citizen scientists.

These data are sometimes considered of low accuracy or biased, limiting their usability for scientific purposes but, on the contrary, citizens can actually gather data of quality comparable to the professional setting^{27,28}, presenting:

- a similar error rate
- a similar degree of variation between observers

For Citizen Science to become an accepted form of science, intentional design with attention to data quality and control is essential, including measures of quality assurance and methods of quality control. Researchers must keep an eye on procedures to enhance data quality undertaken before and during data collection and on the processes for improving quality after data collection.

Quality control is a function of **the scale and of the complexity of the task(s)** performed by participants²⁶.

For example:

- **for simple tasks with a low-medium scale of participant** data quality can be improved by “outsourcing” the thinking to scientists, restricting citizen involvement to straight-forward sample collection tasks while scientists receive, verify, catalogue, and analyze the samples and the resulting data;
- **for simple tasks with numbers of participants** (as in virtual projects), data quality can be improved via crowdsourcing tasks to multiple individuals, with task completion automatically based on algorithm voting or consensus metrics;
- **for a complex task at a small project scale**, options for quality control shift toward expert intervention (on-site expert facilitation and mentoring);
- **for a complex task and a larger number of participants**, statistical pruning, flagging, and other *post hoc* techniques can weed out anomalous data points; machine learning and computational models can be used to create smoothed, interpolated versions of the original data.

27. Lewandowski, E., Caldwell, W., Elmquist, D., & Oberhauser, K. (2017). *Public Perceptions of Citizen Science*. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.77>

28. Crall, A. W., Newman, G. J., Stohlgren, T. J., Holfelder, K. A., Graham, J., & Waller, D. M. (2011). *Assessing citizen science data quality: An invasive species case study*. *Conservation Letters*, 4(6), 433–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00196.x>

6. Benefits of Citizen Science

6.1 Citizen Science goes beyond outreach and Public Engagement

As the first of the 10 principles of Citizen Science states, *Citizen Science projects actively engage citizens in scientific activities that generate new knowledge or understanding*. Public Engagement initiatives *actively engage citizens in scientific activities* as well (figure 4). However, Citizen Science initiatives actually *generate new knowledge or understanding* (figure 5).

*Figure 4 - Public Engagement*²⁹

*Figure 5 - Citizen Science*³⁰

29. Image by zinkevych on Freepik

30. Image from: <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/university-approaches-to-citizen-science-in-the-transition-to-open-science>

6.2 Benefits for researchers and society.

Citizen Science results in several benefits³¹ both for science and for society and at an individual and societal level.

- At the **individual level**, researchers both acquire new data and increase their research capacity, having access to innovative research, while citizens gain scientific literacy and topical knowledge leading them to a behavioural change, including a more active civic participation.
- At the **societal level**, science benefits of more societally relevant researchers, bridging the gap between researchers and citizens and diversifying the topics of the research. At the same time political and environmental benefits emerge such as: data driven policy making, societal relevancy of policy and environments that are improved by citizens' actions.

6.2 Ethical aspects

Despite these benefits, Citizen Science also introduces ethical concerns that must be carefully managed both at the outset and throughout the research process.

"Every technique and every research, as well as every action and choice, tend toward some good, as it seems; therefore, the good has rightly been defined as that to which everything tends"³² said Aristotle in *Nicomachean Ethics*, and it is considered to be one who introduced this word in Ancient Greece. In its strictly philosophical sense, in fact, ethics emerged in the classical world when faith in the existence of objective norms, dictated by religion or custom, began to decline. This shift coincided with the rise of sophism, which replaced this belief with the idea **that laws are made by humans and therefore are subject to human resolution**. Ethics can be considered as a set of norms and values that regulate human behaviour in relation to others, and a criterion that enables humans to judge behaviours, both their own and others³³. Ethics, as a field of philosophical inquiry, has evolved significantly over time: from Greek philosophy to the 20th century, when applied ethics emerged in fields like medicine, technology, and business.

Citizen Science introduces several ethical concerns that need to be addressed before and during the research process. These concerns include ensuring data quality and integrity (see 5.5 paragraph), managing data sharing and intellectual property, preventing conflicts of interest, and avoiding exploitation of participants.

For example, **data sharing** enables others to build upon existing work, fosters discussions, and facilitates critical review but at the same time a careful handling of data is necessary. Issues of **intellectual property** can arise especially when local communities or citizens feel a sense of ownership over the data collected. This is particularly important when the data involves traditional knowledge of local species, climate, and geography,

To ensure ethical research, scientists should establish clear guidelines for citizen involvement, maintain open communication with participants from the start and carefully monitor the work conducted.

31. EUTOPIA Citizen Science Starter Kit: <https://zenodo.org/records/10119036>

32. Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics Book I*, 1094a

33. [A/N] Ethics and morality are often used as synonyms, and in many cases, this is a legitimate usage, but it is important to note that a difference exists: morality corresponds to the set of norms and values of an individual or a group, while ethics, in addition to sharing this set, also includes speculative reflection on norms and values. While morality considers norms and values as given facts, shared by all, ethics seeks to provide a rational and logical explanation for them.

Below there are three case studies with related guidelines that could have solved the ethical problem³⁴.

Figure 6 - Ethical issues and guidelines

34. David B. Resnik, Kevin C. Elliott, Aubrey K. Miller (2015), *A framework for addressing ethical issues in Citizen Science*, Environmental Science & Policy, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.008>

7. Selected projects

In the figures 7-15 we present a selection of projects that have significantly accelerated and enhanced the impact of scientific research.

Figure 7 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: EAR³⁵

35. <https://health-sounds.cl.cam.ac.uk/>

Figure 8 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: ISALA³⁷

Figure 9 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: DeVOTE³⁸

36. Lebeer, S., Ahannach, S., Gehrman, T. et al. *A citizen-science-enabled catalogue of the vaginal microbiome and associated factors*. Nat Microbiol 8, 2183–2195 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-023-01500-0>

37. <https://isala.be/en/>

38. <https://www.votemeanings.eu/>

Figure 10 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: StallCatchers⁴¹

39. Falkenhain, K, Ruiz-Urbe, NE, Haft-Javaherian, M, Ali, M, Stall Catchers, Michelucci, PE, et al. (2020) *A pilot study investigating the effects of voluntary exercise on capillary stalling and cerebral blood flow in the APP/PS1 mouse model of Alzheimer's disease*. PLoS ONE 15(8): e0235691. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0235691>

40. Ali, M, Falkenhain, K, Njiru, BN, Murtaza-Ali, M, Ruiz-Urbe, NE, Haft-Javaherian, M, Stall Catchers, Nishimura, N, Schaffer, CB, Bracko O. *VEGF signalling causes stalls in brain capillaries and reduces cerebral blood flow in Alzheimer's mice*. Brain. 2022 May 24;145(4):1449-1463. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awab387>. PMID: 35048960; PMCID: PMC9150081.

41. <https://stallcatchers.com/main>

Figure 11 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: The Globe Program⁴²

Figure 12 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: The Daily Minor Planet⁴³

42. <https://www.globe.gov/>

43. <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/fulsdauid/the-daily-minor-planet>

eBird is the world's largest biodiversity-related Citizen Science project, **with more than 100 million bird** sightings contributed each year by eBirders around the world

eBird data document **bird distribution, abundance, habitat** use, and trends through checklist data collected within a simple, scientific framework

Birders enter when, where, and how they went birding, and then fill out a checklist of all the birds seen and heard during the outing

eBird's free mobile app allows **offline data collection anywhere in the world**, and the website provides many ways to explore and summarize your data and other observations from the global eBird community

Offline data collection!

Figure 13 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: eBird⁴⁴

FoldIt is a crowdsourcing computer game for performing molecular dynamics simulations of protein dynamics

Applied to biomedical problems, such as Alzheimer's disease, cancer, COVID-19, and Ebola. FoldIt 57000 players are listed among the authors of Nature paper⁴⁵

In 2004, David Baker, awarded with the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry, revolutionized science outreach by launching **Rosetta@home**, enabling volunteers to use their home computers to contribute to protein-folding research: this later inspired Foldit

Citizen Science by a Nobel-Prize laureate!

Figure 14 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: FoldIt⁴⁶

44. <https://ebird.org/home>

45. Cooper, S., Khatib, F., Treuille, A. et al. *Predicting protein structures with a multiplayer online game*. Nature 466, 756–760 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09304>

46. <https://fold.it/>

Figure 15 - Examples of Citizen Science projects: PI@ntNet⁴⁷

8. Final thoughts

Citizen science can bring significant advantages to both scientific research and society.

By engaging in activities like data collection and offering input on study design, data interpretation, dissemination, recruitment, and consent processes, citizens make valuable contributions to research. In turn, participants gain a deeper understanding of scientific principles and methods, often feeling empowered by their ability to influence research outcomes and priorities. Additionally, citizen science fosters stronger social networks, enhancing community capacity to address shared challenges effectively.

With Citizen Science everybody is rewarded: citizens become researchers and researchers increase their sense of citizenship.

In figure 16, we summarize what researchers may benefit from exploiting Citizen Science as a research methodology.

47. <https://plantnet.org/en/about/>

Figure 16 - Key advantages of Citizen Science for researchers